

WHAT IS REINCARNATE

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

KEY FACTS

Demo Case / Value Chain

Flat glass to Flat glass,
Teknikhögden, Stockholm

Lead Partners

Ragn-Sells, DEMO
Consultants, Mainflux, TUB

Innovation(s) applied

BIM for Circular Value Flow
planning

TRL (before → after)

3 → 6

Related Deliverables

D1.1, D1.3, D1.4, D 5.1, D5.2

CONTEXT AND INNOVATION

Circular material flows in construction are hindered by major data limitations. Although pre-demolition audits are required in Sweden and recommended across the EU, the absence of standardized methods and data requirements leads to inconsistent practices and poor comparability. Waste statistics based on broad European Waste Catalogue categories further reduce data usefulness for circular planning. In addition, lifecycle information about building materials is often incomplete, poorly preserved, and not systematically shared between stakeholders, resulting in fragmented and non-interoperable datasets that limit the development of scalable circular business models.

The “flat glass to flat glass” demonstration addresses these challenges by showing how recovered glass from existing buildings can be recycled into new window products through coordinated physical and digital flows. It evaluates how data from inventories, sensors, databases, and value-chain actors can be integrated via the CP-IM platform using a standardized ontology to enable traceability, circularity assessment, and planning. Building on earlier work focused on upstream data collection, the demonstration tests how well inventory data predicts actual recycling outcomes and how standardized data exchange can support closed-loop glass recycling.

The innovation BIM for circular value flow planning (BIM-CVFP) builds on the concept of Circular value flow planning (CVFP). The aim is to enable better planning of material flows and thus enable circular material flows and keeping material at a high quality in the industrial system as long and qualitative as possible. BIM for circular value flow planning is enabled by using a BIM model as the facilitator of data collected from the built environment to estimate the amount of material as well as the material quality and by doing so, enable decision making for increased circularity. Ragn-Sells is demonstrating the innovation by testing how flat glass from old windows are recycled to new flat glass for windows. The demo “flat glass to flat glass” shows the end of that circle while the demonstration “inventory of the material bank”, demonstrates the initiating phase of the innovation.

DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

In collaboration with Akademiska Hus (property owner), a 1960s building scheduled for demolition was selected to demonstrate both the inventory process and the downstream material flow of the Circular Value Flow Planning (CVFP) module. The scope was limited to windows to ensure a focused study aligned with the flat glass ontology developed in earlier work D1.1. Following inventory, windows were carefully dismantled and packaged to preserve their integrity during transport to a treatment facility, where the glass was separated from frames, pre-treated, and quality assured. Fractions unsuitable for high-quality recycling, such as very small particles (“<8 mm”) and rejects, were removed, while the remaining cullet was classified as a product and sent to a glass manufacturer for remelting into new flat glass.

Traceability was ensured through a parallel data flow capturing identifiers from Ragn-Sells ERP and weight measurements at key process stages. Each window delivery was assigned an order number, batches were created during processing, and weights were recorded before and after pre-treatment to verify material origin and quantities. The demonstration focused on comparing estimated glass volumes from different inventory methods with actual recycling outcomes. Results, seen in table 2, showed that 8406 kg of windows yielded 3481 kg of recyclable glass, with the remainder being window frames, downgraded or rejected glass. Inventory methods based on manual surveys and digital scanning achieved reasonably high accuracy, highlighting the importance of reliable data collection for planning circular material flows and estimating environmental benefits.

TECHNICAL HIGHLIGHTS

- Inventory, see demonstration Inventory of the material bank.
- Data sharing (from Ragn-Sells): Weights, customer related information, data collected in the process.
- Data collection: Ragn-Sells RP-system, Ragn-Sells scale system Viktoria, Ragn-Sells CRM-system, data noted in Excel files.
- Integration with CP-IM: module circular value flow planning, uploading Excel and CSV-files in Mainflux, BIM-model uploaded in RE Suite.
- Calculations on CO₂ -savings based on the recycling process.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

In the demonstration, the manual inventory was used as input of the categorizing of the windows according to the following logic:

- Recycling w/o downgrading Scenario - Green
- Recycling Downgrading Scenario - Blue (Laminated)

METHOD	Estimated count of windows: green	Estimated count of windows: blue	Process outcome: green	Process outcome: blue
Initial guess	200	20	127	10
Manual inventory	137	1	127	10
3D scan	138	1	127	10
3D & LiDAR	138	1	127	10

Table 1 - The results from the manual inventory and the inventory used by scanning.

METHOD	Glass – Recyclable (kg)	Glass – Downgrade (kg)	Est. CO ₂ savings (kg)	Accuracy % (Recyclable)
Initial guess	3105	N/A	1646	89%
Manual inventory	3887	22	2060	112%
3D scan	4096	22	2171	118%
3D & LiDAR	5148	22	2728	148%
Process output	3481	285	1844	100%

Table 2 - The accuracy achieved from the manual inventory and the inventory used by scanning.

IMPACTS AND REPLICATION

CATEGORY	IMPACTS	FOCUS	CONTRIBUTION LEVEL
Scientific	I1-I6	Knowledge creation, CP-IM data models, predictive methods	Medium
Societal	I7-I12	Training, awareness, stakeholder engagement	Medium-High
Techno-economic	I13-I18	New value chains, digital tools, replication potential	Medium

The “flat glass to flat glass” demonstration addresses key barriers to circular construction: fragmented data, lack of standardization, and limited traceability, by tracking material and data flows from a real building through recycling into new products.

It validates digital methods and interoperability across systems, demonstrates environmental benefits through traceable reuse, and supports the development of viable circular business models and scalable value chains.

Overall, the case provides a replicable, data-driven approach to operationalizing circular material reuse in the construction sector.

REPLICATION POTENTIAL

This demonstration of the circular value network for flat glass can be replicated with some prerequisites and conditions. The most important thing to have in place is the quality assurance process for flat glass cullet. The circular process, and the downgraded streams (residue and waste) depends on the quality assurance step and its conditions. The separation of glass and frames is a prerequisite for the quality assurance process.

In the inventory of windows all required data that is listed in D1.4. To collect all required data, a tool to test whether windows are laminated or not is needed. To dismantle and handle the windows, competence in this area is required.

To enable traceability in the value chain and CVFP all data specified in D1.4 needs to be collected. Data from an EPR will be necessary to get all data related to construction project and the weights from the process that gives the CO₂ savings.

LINKS

[CP-IM entry through RE Suite and Mainflux](#)

CONTACTS

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